

SOWING THE SEEDS OF ENVIRONMENTAL CARE: RE-GREENING THE MUNICIPALITY OF BAMBAN, TARLAC

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13864895>

ABSTRACT

Climate change, driven by human activities such as deforestation and greenhouse gas emissions, poses significant environmental challenges globally, with intensified effects in the Philippines. In the Municipality of Bamban, Tarlac, rapid urbanization has exacerbated deforestation, contributing to environmental degradation. Project MANASIK (Manage, Act, Save, Intensify Knowledge) was initiated to address these issues by fostering environmental awareness among Grade 12 STEM students and the wider school community through re-greening efforts. This study employed a mixed-methods approach, using pre- and post-project surveys, interviews, and participatory activities like tree planting and nursery establishment to measure the project's impact on environmental awareness. Quantitative data were analyzed using paired T-tests, while qualitative insights were drawn from interviews with stakeholders. Results indicated a significant increase in environmental awareness among both students and community members, with average post-project scores rising from "Low" to "Moderate" and "High" levels of awareness. Challenges encountered during the project included resource limitations and community engagement issues. Nevertheless, Project MANASIK proved effective in increasing awareness of the ecological importance of local trees and fostering a deeper understanding of re-greening practices. The project also demonstrated the vital role that schools and local governments can play in promoting sustainable environmental stewardship, suggesting that further expansion of such initiatives could significantly benefit local communities and ecosystems.

Keywords: Awareness, Biodiversity, Deforestation, Sustainability, Re-greening

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is a pressing global challenge, largely driven by human-induced activities such as greenhouse gas emissions, deforestation, and unsustainable land use practices (Riedy, 2016). These actions contribute to rising global temperatures, altered precipitation patterns, increased occurrences of extreme weather events, and the overall degradation of ecosystems (IPCC, 2018; NASA, 2020). In the Philippines, particularly in the Municipality of Bamban, Tarlac, the situation is exacerbated by rapid urbanization, deforestation, and a general lack of environmental awareness (Lantican, 2015). According to Riedy (2016), human emissions from activities such as fossil fuel combustion and deforestation have led to significant ecological disturbances and climate change. Furthermore, Lantican (2015) emphasized that reforestation, especially using local trees, can mitigate these environmental issues, as local tree species have evolved resilience to local conditions, making them critical in ecological restoration (Fernandez, 2018).

Deforestation and land conversion are major issues in Bamban, Tarlac, where forested areas have been cleared for housing and infrastructure development (Bacallo & Lugma, 2019). As the town becomes increasingly modernized, environmental degradation follows, reducing the availability of natural resources and exacerbating the effects of climate change (Dela Cruz, 2019). The Municipality of Bamban, known for its green landscapes, has not been immune to this modernization, resulting in deforestation and land degradation (Dela Cruz, 2019; Bacallo & Lugma, 2019). Reforestation and local tree planting efforts can help reverse these impacts by restoring critical habitats and reducing carbon emissions (Smith et al., 2021).

In response to these environmental challenges, Project MANASIK (Manage, Act, Save, Intensify Knowledge) was initiated to promote environmental care among Grade 12 Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) students and other members of the school community (Sali, 2016). The project focused on educating participants about the importance of planting local tree species to mitigate the effects of climate change and promote sustainable environmental practices (Lehmann, 2019). Re-greening efforts, such as this, play a vital role in combating climate change by restoring ecological balance and enhancing the resilience of ecosystems (Carey, 2020). Youth engagement in such initiatives is critical, as it encourages long-term sustainability and builds environmental stewardship (Jensen, 2017).

The general problem addressed by this study is, "How may sowing the seeds of environmental care be intensified among the school community members in re-greening the entire Municipality of Bamban, Tarlac?"

Research Questions

1. How may the level of awareness on re-greening before and after the implementation of the School-Based Project MANASIK in the Municipality of Bamban, Tarlac be described by

1.1 Students

1.2 Other School Community Members

2. Is there a significant difference between the level of awareness of the Grade 12 Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) students and other school community members before and after the implementation of School-Based Project MANASIK?
3. What are the re-greening challenges encountered by the program implementing agency?
4. What are the contributions of the school community in re-greening the Municipality of Bamban, Tarlac?
5. How may the proposed Community-Based Project MANASIK be intensified in re-greening the entire Municipality of Bamban, Tarlac?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, integrating both qualitative and quantitative research techniques to assess the impact of Project MANASIK. The respondents included 45 Grade 12 STEM students and 45 other community members (primarily parents and guardians) from San Roque National High School. The study was conducted in 15 barangays within Bamban, Tarlac, such as Anupul, San Nicolas, and Sto. Niño during the school year 2020 to 2021.

Data collection involved several methods. First, a 4-point Likert scale survey was administered to assess the respondents' awareness of re-greening before and after the implementation of Project MANASIK. The questionnaire focused on their understanding of local trees, reforestation, and environmental sustainability. In addition to the surveys, in-depth interviews were conducted with key stakeholders, including local officials, forestry experts from the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR), and representatives from the Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Office (PENRO). These interviews provided insights into the challenges faced during the re-greening efforts, including resource limitations and community engagement issues.

Furthermore, the study included participatory activities in which students actively engaged in tree planting, nursery establishment, and seed germination experiments. They collected high-quality seeds from local tree species, such as Alibangbang (*Bauhinia monandra*) and Talisay (*Terminalia catappa*), and maintained a small-scale forest nursery over a 25-day period. The quantitative data from the surveys were analyzed using paired t-tests to determine whether there were significant changes in awareness levels before and after the project, while qualitative data from interviews and participatory activities were analyzed thematically.

RESULTS

Table 1

Overall Computed Mean Values on the Level of Awareness of Grade 12 Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) Students Before and After the Implementation of School-Based Project MANASIK

Student	Before	Descriptive Interpretation	After	Descriptive Interpretation
1	1.76	Low Level of Awareness	3.53	High Level of Awareness
2	1.41	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.46	Moderate Level of Awareness
3	1.55	Low Level of Awareness	3.49	Moderate Level of Awareness
4	1.53	Low Level of Awareness	3.55	High Level of Awareness
5	1.54	Low Level of Awareness	3.54	High Level of Awareness
6	1.56	Low Level of Awareness	3.55	High Level of Awareness
7	1.58	Low Level of Awareness	3.48	Moderate Level of Awareness
8	1.59	Low Level of Awareness	3.46	Moderate Level of Awareness
9	1.53	Low Level of Awareness	3.44	Moderate Level of Awareness
10	1.55	Low Level of Awareness	3.46	Moderate Level of Awareness
11	1.60	Low Level of Awareness	3.58	High Level of Awareness
12	1.61	Low Level of Awareness	3.55	High Level of Awareness
13	1.58	Low Level of Awareness	3.51	High Level of Awareness
14	1.48	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.53	High Level of Awareness
15	1.45	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.53	High Level of Awareness
16	1.54	Low Level of Awareness	3.44	Moderate Level of Awareness
17	1.65	Low Level of Awareness	3.48	Moderate Level of Awareness
18	1.45	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.56	High Level of Awareness
19	1.56	Low Level of Awareness	3.41	Moderate Level of Awareness
20	1.56	Low Level of Awareness	3.54	High Level of Awareness
21	1.48	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.50	Moderate Level of Awareness
22	1.55	Low Level of Awareness	3.51	High Level of Awareness
23	1.48	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.44	Moderate Level of Awareness
24	1.49	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.51	High Level of Awareness
25	1.44	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.56	High Level of Awareness
26	1.51	Low Level of Awareness	3.44	Moderate Level of Awareness
27	1.53	Low Level of Awareness	3.49	Moderate Level of Awareness
28	1.43	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.54	High Level of Awareness
29	1.54	Low Level of Awareness	3.45	Moderate Level of Awareness
30	1.45	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.68	High Level of Awareness
31	1.55	Low Level of Awareness	3.66	High Level of Awareness
32	1.53	Low Level of Awareness	3.40	Moderate Level of Awareness
33	1.54	Low Level of Awareness	3.54	High Level of Awareness
34	1.53	Low Level of Awareness	3.56	High Level of Awareness
35	1.45	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.61	High Level of Awareness
36	1.54	Low Level of Awareness	3.66	High Level of Awareness
37	1.54	Low Level of Awareness	3.65	High Level of Awareness
38	1.61	Low Level of Awareness	3.50	Moderate Level of Awareness
39	1.63	Low Level of Awareness	3.48	Moderate Level of Awareness
40	1.54	Low Level of Awareness	3.46	Moderate Level of Awareness
41	1.61	Low Level of Awareness	3.59	High Level of Awareness
42	1.50	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.60	High Level of Awareness
43	1.53	Low Level of Awareness	3.48	Moderate Level of Awareness
44	1.54	Low Level of Awareness	3.46	Moderate Level of Awareness
45	1.55	Low Level of Awareness	3.30	Moderate Level of Awareness

Total	1.54	Low Level of Awareness	3.51	High Level of Awareness
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Table 2

Overall Computed Mean Values on the Level of Awareness of the Other School Community Members Before and After the Implementation of School-Based Project MANASIK

Other School Community Members	Before	Descriptive Interpretation	After	Descriptive Interpretation
1	1.50	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.43	Moderate Level of Awareness
2	1.53	Low Level of Awareness	3.48	Moderate Level of Awareness
3	1.65	Low Level of Awareness	3.46	Moderate Level of Awareness
4	1.63	Low Level of Awareness	3.49	Moderate Level of Awareness
5	1.58	Low Level of Awareness	3.53	High Level of Awareness
6	1.55	Low Level of Awareness	3.50	Moderate Level of Awareness
7	1.60	Low Level of Awareness	3.46	Moderate Level of Awareness
8	1.60	Low Level of Awareness	3.46	Moderate Level of Awareness
9	1.58	Low Level of Awareness	3.40	Moderate Level of Awareness
10	1.55	Low Level of Awareness	3.40	Moderate Level of Awareness
11	1.50	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.54	High Level of Awareness
12	1.53	Low Level of Awareness	3.49	Moderate Level of Awareness
13	1.45	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.44	Moderate Level of Awareness
14	1.50	Low Level of Awareness	3.35	Moderate Level of Awareness
15	1.60	Low Level of Awareness	3.51	High Level of Awareness
16	1.53	Low Level of Awareness	3.43	Moderate Level of Awareness
17	1.60	Low Level of Awareness	3.50	Moderate Level of Awareness
18	1.53	Low Level of Awareness	3.46	Moderate Level of Awareness
19	1.55	Low Level of Awareness	3.40	Moderate Level of Awareness
20	1.60	Low Level of Awareness	3.50	Moderate Level of Awareness
21	1.60	Low Level of Awareness	3.50	Moderate Level of Awareness
22	1.50	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.44	Moderate Level of Awareness
23	1.60	Low Level of Awareness	3.43	Moderate Level of Awareness
24	1.48	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.51	High Level of Awareness
25	1.60	Low Level of Awareness	3.51	High Level of Awareness
26	1.55	Low Level of Awareness	3.51	High Level of Awareness
27	1.73	Low Level of Awareness	3.46	Moderate Level of Awareness
28	1.45	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.45	Moderate Level of Awareness
29	1.50	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.35	Moderate Level of Awareness
30	1.65	Low Level of Awareness	3.45	Moderate Level of Awareness
31	1.53	Low Level of Awareness	3.54	High Level of Awareness
32	1.53	Low Level of Awareness	3.45	Moderate Level of Awareness
33	1.55	Low Level of Awareness	3.51	High Level of Awareness
34	1.50	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.38	Moderate Level of Awareness
35	1.58	Low Level of Awareness	3.38	Moderate Level of Awareness
36	1.58	Low Level of Awareness	3.38	Moderate Level of Awareness

37	1.50	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.48	Moderate Level of Awareness
38	1.48	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.44	Moderate Level of Awareness
39	1.58	Low Level of Awareness	3.48	Moderate Level of Awareness
40	1.50	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.43	Moderate Level of Awareness
41	1.58	Low Level of Awareness	3.43	Moderate Level of Awareness
42	1.63	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.43	Moderate Level of Awareness
43	1.50	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.43	Moderate Level of Awareness
44	1.60	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.45	Moderate Level of Awareness
45	1.48	Very Low Level of Awareness	3.48	Moderate Level of Awareness
Total	1.55	Low Level of Awareness	3.45	Moderate Level of Awareness

Table 3

Significant Difference between the Level of Awareness of Grade 12 STEM Students and Other School Community Members on Re-greening Before and After the Implementation of the School-Based Project MANASIK (N=90)

Level of Awareness	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision	Remarks
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference						
				Lower	Upper					
BEFORE-AFTER	-1.93978	.09610	.01013	-1.95991	-1.91965	-191.484	89	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

DISCUSSION

The results from Table 1 reveal a significant increase in the level of environmental awareness among Grade 12 STEM students following the implementation of Project MANASIK. Prior to the project, the students' overall awareness was categorized as "Low," with an average mean score of 1.54. Individual scores ranged from "Very Low" (1.41) to "Low" (1.76). After the project, a notable improvement occurred, with the overall mean increasing to 3.51, reflecting a "High Level of Awareness." This finding aligns with Bandura's Social Learning Theory, which emphasizes that individuals learn by observing and modeling behaviors, particularly through interactive and hands-on activities (Bandura, 1977). The practical elements of Project MANASIK, such as tree planting and environmental education, were instrumental in increasing awareness among students by immersing them in the environmental challenges they were learning about (Bookchin, 1982; Lantican, 2015).

Many students who initially had very low or low awareness levels advanced to moderate or high awareness categories. This marked increase highlights the

effectiveness of Project MANASIK in significantly enhancing students' understanding of re-greening practices and environmental stewardship. The project's hands-on approach and educational interventions played a critical role in transforming the students' awareness, leading to higher engagement with environmental issues (Cochane, 2007; Gad, 2019). This is consistent with Kolb's Experiential Learning Theory, which argues that learning is most effective when learners are actively engaged in meaningful experiences (Kolb, 1984).

Table 2 presents the significant improvement in the level of environmental awareness among the other school community members following the implementation of Project MANASIK. Before the project, the overall mean awareness score was 1.55, indicating a "Low Level of Awareness." Individual pre-project scores ranged from 1.45 to 1.73, with many participants falling into the "Very Low" or "Low" categories. After the project, the overall mean increased to 3.45, indicating a "Moderate Level of Awareness." The social learning that occurred within the broader school community demonstrates the power of collective action, as highlighted by Kuo (2012), who stressed the importance of group involvement in fostering environmental consciousness.

Most participants shifted to the moderate awareness category, with some even reaching a "High Level of Awareness" (e.g., participant 5 and 11 scoring 3.53 and 3.54, respectively). This upward trend demonstrates the effectiveness of Project MANASIK in raising environmental awareness and re-greening practices within the broader school community (Angelsen, 2007). The use of community engagement and collaborative learning activities mirrors the principles of Collectivism, which emphasize the collective responsibility of the community in addressing environmental issues (Kuo, 2012; Anguelovski, 2018).

The results presented in Table 3 indicate a statistically significant difference in the level of awareness between Grade 12 STEM students and other school community members before and after the implementation of Project MANASIK. The paired t-test revealed a mean difference of -1.93978, with a standard deviation of 0.09610 and a standard error mean of 0.01013. The 95% confidence interval of the difference ranged from -1.95991 to -1.91965, with a t-value of -191.484 and 89 degrees of freedom. The significance level ($p \leq 0.05$) led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, confirming that Project MANASIK had a substantial positive impact on improving the awareness levels of both groups. These results underscore the project's effectiveness in raising environmental consciousness among students and community members, demonstrating a marked shift in their understanding of re-greening initiatives after participating in the program (Lemenih & Kassa, 2014).

Furthermore, the challenges encountered by the implementing agency in re-greening efforts, such as delays in budget release and issues related to land claimants, mirror the findings of similar environmental projects that have highlighted financial and logistical barriers to successful implementation (Hirons & Thomas, 2017). Additionally, the disorganization and financial incapability of Private Organizations (PO) to independently sustain re-greening projects were noted, which corroborates previous

research showing the heavy reliance of community-based projects on government support (Reynolds & Peres, 2006). The limited availability of seedlings from the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) further highlights the need for enhanced coordination and resource allocation in future re-greening initiatives (Stuart, 2018).

Moreover, the intensive participation in School-Based Project MANASIK enabled school community members to contribute significantly to re-greening the Municipality of Bamban, Tarlac. This is in line with studies that emphasize the role of schools as vital channels for environmental education and awareness, particularly in fostering long-term environmental stewardship among the youth (Blicharska & Mikusiński, 2014; Toyama et al., 2015). Schools serve as an effective medium for raising awareness, as their structured learning environments can instill values of environmental protection and restoration in students (Cochane, 2007).

Finally, in terms of intensifying the level of awareness on re-greening, the researcher's proposal on community-based Project MANASIK was greatly supported by the Local Government Units (LGUs), which played a crucial role in ensuring the success of the project (Urzedo et al., 2019). The active involvement and approval from municipal leaders and barangay captains reflect the importance of local governance in environmental sustainability efforts (Republic Act No. 9147, 2001). This partnership between schools and LGUs highlights the need for collective action in addressing environmental challenges and promoting re-greening practices at the community level (Saguin, 2012).

Conclusions

The students initially exhibited a very low level of awareness regarding the ecosystem services of local trees, germplasm collection, seed morphology, and nursery setup, as evidenced by mean scores ranging from 1.23 to 1.30. After the implementation of Project MANASIK, there was a significant improvement, with the overall awareness level of the other school community members increasing from 1.55, indicating a low level of awareness, to 3.45, reflecting a moderate level of awareness. This demonstrates that the project had a positive and substantial impact on the participants' understanding of re-greening practices, leading to an increased environmental consciousness within the school community.

There was a statistically significant difference in the level of awareness before and after the implementation of Project MANASIK for both Grade 12 students and other school community members, as indicated by the p-value ($p \leq 0.05$). The computed t-value of -191.484, with a 95% confidence interval between -1.95991 and -1.91965, further supports the rejection of the null hypothesis. These results highlight the significant improvement in environmental awareness as a direct result of the project, indicating that both students and other school community members gained valuable knowledge and understanding of re-greening initiatives.

Several challenges impacted the re-greening efforts, including unpredictable weather, delays in budget release, land claimant disputes, disorganization within private organizations (PO), and inadequate human resources. There was heavy reliance on the government for financial support, and private organizations struggled to independently initiate and sustain re-greening projects. The limited supply of seedlings from the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR), along with poor participation from other government agencies, exacerbated the difficulties in sustaining re-greening efforts. These challenges highlight the need for better coordination and resource management to ensure the success of future re-greening projects.

Schools played a vital role in re-greening campaigns through their intensive participation in Project MANASIK. They were particularly effective in raising awareness among students and the broader school community about the importance of protecting and restoring local trees. The participation of students, as future environmental stewards, is crucial. Their involvement in re-greening activities serves as a foundation for their future contributions to environmental sustainability. By actively engaging in these projects, students gain a deeper appreciation for nature and are better equipped to support conservation efforts in the future.

The intensification of Project MANASIK received strong support from local government units, with key stakeholders, including the Municipal Mayor, Councilor, and 15 barangay captains, showing approval and appreciation for the initiative. This endorsement from local authorities highlights the potential for broader community-based re-greening efforts, fostering collaboration and further strengthening environmental conservation awareness across the Municipality of Bamban, Tarlac. The success of Project MANASIK not only demonstrates the value of community involvement in re-greening projects but also paves the way for future initiatives to expand and build on this foundation.

Recommendations

Schools must strictly implement the existing policies on environmental care and protection since these can be venues for students' actions in learning more about and caring for the natural environment. For instance, DepEd Order no. 93, s. 2011 mandated programs, activities, various forms and targets pertinent to the Youth for Environment in Schools Organization (YES-O) issued to primary and secondary schools can be utilized in uplifting the students' awareness regarding the environment in caring for it. Observance of Arbor Day every 25th of June throughout the nation planting trees and ornamental plants and other forms of relevant activities.

The utilization of constructed and validated data collection tools is recommended in similar studies. Likewise, it is also recommended that the validity and reliability of these tools be further tested.

The government must strengthen its partnership with the Private Organization (PO) to expand re-greening projects, set accurate schedules of the planting of seedlings,

early release of the budget, solving the problem on land claiming, reconcile misunderstanding of the members of PO. Increasing manpower in planting seedlings is necessary to succeed in re-greening.

School communities must establish an arboretum of local trees that would further intensify re-greening campaign. It is high time for local communities to have an extensive information awareness campaign (ex. making brochures or placards) on the importance of various natural resources, the destruction of local trees due to human activities and ways of preserving and conserving it for the benefit of the future generations. The establishment of the arboretum is one of the proposed projects needed to remind each student of the ecosystem services offered by the local trees to animals. The success of sowing the seeds of environmental care project depends on its conformity with the existing local trees management manuals. Individuals who plan to conduct such a project must study this scientific methodology concerning sowing the seeds in re-greening the Municipality.

The proposed Community-Based Project MANASIK should build a strong partnership in caring for the natural environment. Unity and cooperation of the members of the community must be established since these are the keys to solving environmental problems like local trees forest decline. The dissemination of the constructed information materials about local trees protection conservation is highly recommended to raise awareness about the importance of this activity and to guide others in their respective sowing the seeds of local trees projects. It is the responsibility of educational institutions to inform and empower their learners to act for the betterment of the natural environment. Adhere the Division Memorandum No. 99, series of 2020 "Strengthening the Implementation of the Youth for Environment in Schools Organization (YES-O)" consisting of the following activities related to Project MANASIK are nursery establishment and Tree-Planting Activities (in pursuant with DepEd Memorandum no. 187, series 2018 entitled Pilot Implementation of the School Inside Garden (SIGA) Program and DECS Memorandum No. 77 s. 1995 entitled The School Inside a Garden (SIGA).

Future researchers are encouraged to expand the scope of study by including other municipalities for comparative analysis and to conduct longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impacts of projects like MANASIK on environmental behavior. Incorporating both quantitative and qualitative methods will provide a more comprehensive understanding, while exploring technological tools and innovative educational approaches, such as gamification, could enhance engagement. Researchers should also focus on how such projects can influence policymaking and address barriers to re-greening, such as funding and logistical challenges, to ensure the sustainability and broader application of these initiatives.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In compliance with ethical standards, this study was conducted with strict adherence to ethical guidelines and principles. Prior to data collection, informed consent

was obtained from all participants, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights, including the right to withdraw at any time without any consequences. The privacy and confidentiality of participants were strictly maintained, and all data were anonymized to protect their identities. Additionally, the study followed institutional ethical protocols and received approval from the relevant ethics review board. No conflicts of interest or biases influenced the study, and all efforts were made to ensure the accuracy, honesty, and integrity of the research process. The environmental re-greening initiatives discussed were implemented with respect for local ecosystems and with the involvement and consent of the community stakeholders.

Acknowledgments

The researcher extends sincere gratitude to all individuals and organizations who contributed to the success of this study. Special thanks are given to the school administrators, teachers, and staff of the participating schools for their invaluable support and cooperation during the implementation of Project MANASIK. Deep appreciation is also extended to the Grade 12 STEM students and the other school community members who willingly participated in the study. The researcher is grateful to the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) and local government units of the Municipality of Bamban, Tarlac, for their guidance and assistance in the re-greening initiatives. A heartfelt thank you is also given to family and friends for their unwavering encouragement throughout the research process. Lastly, the researcher acknowledges the support and inspiration from academic mentors, whose guidance has been crucial to the completion of this research study and project.

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